

Article

Insight into the Morphology, Hydrophobicity and Swelling Behavior of TiO₂-Reinforced Polyurethane

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Abstract: In this research, the structure, morphology, hydrophobicity and swelling behavior of a polyurethane (PU) network and its composites (PUCs) were examined. PUCs were synthesized by the incorporation of different percentages (0.5, 1 and 2 wt.%) of unmodified or surface-modified TiO₂ nanoparticles into a PU network based on polycaprolactone, aliphatic hyperbranched polyester and isophorone diisocyanate. In order to improve interfacial interactions, the surface of the TiO₂ nanoparticles was chemically modified with lauryl gallate. The impact of the presence and content of unmodified or surface-modified TiO₂ nanoparticles on the cross-sectional and surface morphology, swelling behavior and hydrophobicity of the PU network was assessed by different experiments. The obtained findings revealed that the incorporation of TiO₂ nanoparticles brought a more pronounced irregular cross-sectional and rougher surface morphology, better microphase separation, higher values of the equilibrium swelling degree in tetrahydrofuran and toluene, and altered water contact angles compared to the neat PU. Based on the collected results, the practical applicability of the prepared PUCs may be in the area of protective coatings.

Keywords: polyurethane composites; structure; morphology; titanium dioxide nanoparticles; swelling behavior; hydrophobicity

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1. Introduction

Polyurethanes (PUs) are one of the most diverse polymer materials and therefore one of the most widely used worldwide. Today, their application is so widespread that they are used in the design of medical equipment and drug delivery vehicles, adhesives, elastomers, coatings, footwear and clothing, rigid and flexible foams, etc. [1–4]. Their wide practical applicability stems from the fact that they have good chemical, electrical and abrasion resistance, high bearing capacity, durability, flexibility, etc. Traditionally, PUs are synthesized by the reaction between polyols and isocyanates, but, lately, researchers have increasingly been resorting to new synthetic pathways that involve catalyzed non-isocyanate reactions in order to improve PU biocompatibility [5,6]. Their unique and

tunable features, which can be easily adjusted by changing the structure of the reactants, depend also on the final molecular weight of the PUs, appearance of crystallization and additional interactions, density and surface morphology of the PUs, presence and extent of microphase separation, etc. [7,8].

Although PUs have good performances, there is a constant need for their improvement and promotion among the scientific and industrial ranks. Therefore, the creation of PUs with good water and solvent resistance and hydrolytic and enzymatic stability is always in demand. The incorporation of nanofillers into a PU structure is one of the most commonly used approaches to enhance the surface and weathering performances of PUs and extend their durability and thermal stability [9–17]. Due to the high surface/volume ratio, even with an extremely small amount of nanofiller, it is possible to achieve superior performances of PU composites compared to pure PUs. Still, to achieve a positive effect of added nanofillers on the targeted features of PUs, their suitable dispersion without agglomeration is a basic requirement. However, because of the large particle surface energy and incompatibility with the organic polymer matrix, nanoparticles tend to stick together and form agglomerates. Nano-sized TiO₂ is intensively used as nanofiller for PUs due to its outstanding performances. Many attempts have been made to achieve the homogenous distribution of TiO₂ nanoparticles in PUs and increase the contact surface and interfacial interactions between the TiO₂ nanofiller and polymer matrix [18–20]. One way is to use a sonification process during preparation in which mechanical shear force is applied to separate the nanoparticles and prevent their agglomeration. However, this method does not prove to be sufficient to completely prevent the agglomeration of nanoparticles in PU since interfacial forces between individual nanoparticles are often stronger than applied mechanical forces [21]. Reid et al. [22] improved the dispersion of TiO₂ nanoparticles in PU by their in situ synthesis in a prepolymer solution. Furthermore, Polizos et al. [23] synthesized in situ TiO₂ nanoparticles in polyethylene glycol and then used the prepared composite as a filler for commercial thermoplastic PU in order to improve its electrical insulation properties. Accordingly, the researchers also tried to improve interactions between the PU matrix and nanoparticles by adequate surface modification of the nanoparticles [24–27]. Sabzi et al. [24] showed that the surface modification of TiO₂ nanoparticles with amino propyl trimethoxy silane enables their good dispersion and enhances the UV resistance and mechanical properties of the prepared PU clear coatings. Similarly, Wu et al. [28] achieved the uniform dispersion of TiO₂ nanoparticles in PU elastomers by their surface modification with a silane coupling agent. Furthermore, Behniafar et al. [29] showed that covalent linkage between TiO₂ nanoparticles and PU can be formed using NH₂-functionalized TiO₂ nanoparticles. Zhang et al. [30] reported that the grafting of hyperbranched polymers onto TiO₂ nanoparticle surfaces via a thiol-yne click chemistry reaction could decrease their tendency to aggregate within the PU matrix, increase surface roughness and, consequently, lead to better hydrophobicity. The application of TiO₂ nanoparticles can slow down the photo-aging of the PUs, which includes the prevention of double bond oxidation, crosslinking breaks, the scission of different segments that can lead to discoloration and the appearance of cracks and coating delamination, all because of the great index of refraction of UV radiation [31,32]. Furthermore, TiO₂ nanoparticles can also interact with soft or hard segments of PU, creating additional chemical or physical interactions, leading also to the improvement of PU features.

This study is a continuation of our research considering polyurethane composites (PUCs) based on polycaprolactone (PCL), isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), aliphatic hyperbranched polyesters and unmodified and modified TiO₂ nanoparticles. In our previous works, we examined the structural, thermal and mechanical properties of a series of PUs [33,34] and their composites [35]. In this paper, we investigate the surface properties

of PU composites by examining their surface and cross-sectional morphology, swelling behavior, and hydrophobicity.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) diol (PCL, $M_n \approx 2000$ g/mol, from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany) was dried at 80 °C for 12 h before use. Boltorn[®] hydroxy-functional aliphatic hyperbranched polyester of the second pseudo generation (BH-20, $M_n = 1340$ g/mol) [36] from Perstorp Specialty Chemicals AB (Malmö, Sweden) was dried under a vacuum for 48 h at 50 °C. Isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI, from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany) was used as received. The stannous octoate ($\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$, from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany, purity 95%) was used as a catalyst. Solvents, *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (DMAc, from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany, purity 99%) and tetrahydrofuran (THF, from J. T. Baker, Gliwice, Poland, purity 99.99%) were previously purified and kept over molecular sieves (0.4 nm) before synthesis, while toluene (from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany, purity 99.9%) was used as received. Dodecyl (lauryl) gallate (LG) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). A commercially available TiO_2 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Acetonitrile was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany) and used as received.

2.2. Preparation of Polyurethane Composites

The complete procedures for the preparation of the neat PU based on PCL, IPDI and BH-20; the surface modification of TiO_2 nanoparticles with lauryl gallate (TiO_2 -LG); and the synthesis of PUCs based on unmodified TiO_2 and TiO_2 -LG as nanofillers are described elsewhere [33,35]. Briefly, 2 g of TiO_2 was introduced into a 100 cm³ solution of lauryl gallate in acetonitrile (0.01 mol/dm³), followed by 10 min mixing in an ultrasonic bath. After the solution was left overnight, TiO_2 -LG nanoparticles were precipitated using a centrifuge, washed twice with acetonitrile and, finally, dried in a vacuum oven at 40 °C. Unmodified and modified TiO_2 nanoparticles were added in amounts of 0.5, 1 and 2 wt.% relative to the total weight of reactants. In order to provide a homogenous dispersion of nanoparticles within the PU network structure, pre-determined amounts of nanofiller and THF were mixed in an ultrasonic bath for 20 min at room temperature. For the neat PU and all PUCs, the stoichiometric ratio between –NCO and –OH groups was kept constant at 1.1. At the end of the reaction, the mixtures were poured into Teflon dishes and placed in a force-draft oven to enable the curing of samples, first at 60 °C for 24 h and then at 80 °C for 3 h. The drying of samples was performed in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 24 h. All samples were stored in desiccators at room temperature for two weeks before characterization.

Prepared PU composites are designated as PUC/Ti-xx or PUC/LG-xx, where “Ti” and “LG” indicate that they were prepared with TiO_2 or TiO_2 -LG nanoparticles, respectively, while “xx” denotes the weight percentages of the added nanoparticles. The neat polyurethane network (without nanoparticles) is denoted simply as PU. Figure 1a shows the reactants and nanoparticles, while Figure 1b shows the preparation pathway of the PUCs.

2.3. Characterization

FTIR analysis was performed in attenuated total reflection (Everest ATR) mode using an FT-IR Nicolet SUMMIT (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) spectrometer. All spectra were recorded at the same conditions: resolution of 2 cm⁻¹, 64 scans and wave number from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹.

The cross-sectional surface of the neat PU and its composites was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using the XL30 scanning electron microscope (Philips, Eind-

hoven, The Netherlands), which contains a Gemini column (Zeiss Supra 35 VP, Oberkochen, Germany). All samples were Au-coated (15 nm thickness) in a high-vacuum evaporator before taking measurements.

Figure 1. (a) Reactants and unmodified and modified TiO₂ nanoparticles and (b) reaction pathway for the preparation of the neat PU and its composites.

Surface topography and roughness of the neat PU and its composites were examined using NTEGRA Prima atomic force microscope (NT-MDT, Moscow, Russia). Measurements were taken using NT-MDT NSG01/Pt silicon cantilevers. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) investigations collected 3D height and 2D phase AFM images of the neat PU and its composite films, measured under ambient conditions, using intermittent contact mode at a scan size of 20 × 20 μm².

TEM micrographs of PUC films (with 0.5 and 2 wt.% of unmodified and modified TiO₂ nanoparticles) were recorded on a JEOL JEM-1400 Plus Electron microscope (Jeol Ltd., Mitaka, Japan), operating at a voltage of 120 kV with a LaB₆ filament, at 60k× magnification. Samples were first cut into 2 mm strips and then embedded in Araldite (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland) at an elevated temperature. The PUC ultra-thin films were cut with a diamond knife (Diatome, Nidau, Switzerland) on Leica UC6 ultramicrotome (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany) and afterwards mounted on holey-carbon coated grids.

Equilibrium swelling degrees, q_e , of the neat PU and its composites in toluene and THF were determined by utilizing the conventional gravimetric method and the following equation:

$$q_e = \frac{w - w_0}{w_0} \quad (1)$$

where w_0 and w are the sample weights before and after the swelling. Square test specimens ($1.0 \times 1.0 \times 0.1 \text{ cm}^3$) were immersed in a selected solvent at room temperature and the weight of the swollen squares was periodically measured until a constant value was reached. The average q_e of each sample was calculated using data from three separate swelling measurements.

The water absorption ability of the neat PU and its composites was examined by immersion of the investigated samples ($1.0 \times 1.0 \times 0.1 \text{ cm}^3$) in distilled water for 48 h at room temperature. The water absorption (in weight percent), WA, was calculated by

$$WA = \frac{w_W - w_{W0}}{w_{W0}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where w_{W0} is the weight before water immersion, while w_W is the weight after the removal of the excess water from the sample. The average WA of samples was calculated by conducting three measurements for each sample.

Water contact angle (WCA) measurements were carried out on the Drop shape analyzer (DSA25 instrument, Hamburg, Germany) using the sessile drop method and Krüss Advance version 1.11.2.25901 software. For all measurements, the conditions during recordings were the same (room humidity of 55%, room temperature of 23 °C and needle diameter of 0.513 mm). The presented WCA values are the mean of five replicates.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. FTIR Spectroscopy

For examination of the structure of the TiO₂ nanoparticles, neat PU and its composites, the ATR-FTIR spectroscopic method was used. The obtained FTIR spectra are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. (a) FTIR spectra of TiO₂ nanoparticles, neat PU and prepared PUCs with 0.5 and 2 wt.% of TiO₂ nanoparticles and (b) FTIR spectra of TiO₂-LG nanoparticles, neat PU and prepared PUCs with 0.5 and 2 wt.% of TiO₂-LG nanoparticles.

Figure 2a shows the FTIR spectrum of unmodified TiO₂ nanoparticles, where intense and broad bands at ~ 3300 and $\sim 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which originated from the stretching vibrations of $-\text{OH}$ and $\text{Ti}-\text{O}$ groups, were noticeable, respectively. Apart from that, in the FTIR spectrum of the TiO₂-LG nanoparticles (Figure 2b), the bands from LG were visible, indicating the successful functionalization of the TiO₂ nanoparticles [37]. These bands were visible at

$\sim 2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$, 1700 cm^{-1} , 1610 cm^{-1} and 1220 cm^{-1} and arose from the stretching vibrations of the $-\text{CH}_2$, $\text{C}=\text{O}$, aromatic ring and $\text{C}-\text{O}$ groups, respectively.

FTIR spectra of the neat PU and its composites had similar bands at $3320\text{--}3365\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (stretching vibrations of $-\text{NH}$ groups), 2950 and 2865 cm^{-1} (asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups, respectively), 1725 cm^{-1} (stretching vibrations of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups), 1550 and 1240 cm^{-1} (stretching vibrations of amide II and amide III, respectively), 1460 cm^{-1} (deformation vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups), and $1040\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ groups). The presence of quoted bands in the FTIR spectra of the prepared samples unequivocally confirmed the formation of a polyurethane structure [38,39].

3.2. SEM Analysis

SEM analysis was performed to examine and compare the micromorphology of the neat PU and its composites. The recorded micrographs of all samples (Figure 3) were obtained on the fractured cross-sectional films, previously frozen in liquid N_2 and coated with Au.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs taken of the cross-sectional surfaces of neat PU and its composites (magnification $10k\times$).

As can be seen from the obtained micrographs, the neat PU had an irregular cross-sectional surface morphology. On the other hand, the micrographs showing the cross-sectional surface of the PUCs showed the impact of the TiO_2 nanoparticles on the morphology of the PU. PUCs with the lowest content of TiO_2 nanoparticles (samples with 0.5 wt.%) had less irregular and smoother cross-sectional surfaces than neat PU, while on the surface of PUCs with higher contents of TiO_2 nanoparticles (1 and 2 wt.%), the creation of certain micro-structures (clusters or agglomerates) [35] of various sizes could be observed (predominantly visible and noticeable on the cross-sectional surface of PUC/Ti-2.0).

It seems that the homogeneous dispersion of unmodified TiO₂ nanoparticles inside the PU was quite challenging to achieve due to their high tendency to stick together [40,41]. Agglomerates, which certainly formed in the PUC if a higher content of unmodified TiO₂ nanoparticles was added, can be regarded as weak points that can aggravate the mechanical properties of PUCs [42]. Contrarily, SEM micrographs of PUC/LG cross-sectional surfaces indicated that better dispersion of the TiO₂ nanoparticles was accomplished after their surface modification with LG.

3.3. AFM Analysis

AFM analysis was performed to investigate the surface topography and roughness of the neat PU and PUCs. The obtained 3D height and 2D phase images at scan size $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ and in intermittent contact mode are presented in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. Also, the surface roughness values, determined using Gwyddion 2.61 (free and open-source software, Czech Metrology Institute) software, are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Surface roughness of neat PU and its composite films (scan sizes: $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$).

Sample	R_a^1 (nm)	R_q^2 (nm)
PU	334	408
PUC/Ti-0.5	440	545
PUC/Ti-1.0	439	533
PUC/Ti-2.0	493	589
PUC/LG-0.5	367	474
PUC/LG-1.0	353	431
PUC/LG-2.0	446	548

¹ R_a —(mean roughness) the average value of the surface height deviations taken within a presented area. ² R_q —(RMS—root mean square) the standard deviation of the height values within a presented area.

Figure 4. The 3D height AFM images of the surfaces of neat PU and PUCs. Scan size: $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Figure 5. The 2D phase AFM images of the surfaces of neat PU and its composites. Scan size: $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$.

From Figure 4, it can be observed that the surface of the PUCs became rougher after the incorporation of TiO_2 nanoparticles (Table 1), whereby surface roughness values were the highest for composites with 2 wt.% of TiO_2 nanoparticles (modified or unmodified). It can also be observed that values of surface roughness were higher for composites prepared with unmodified TiO_2 nanoparticles. The reason for this lies in the fact that long alkyl chains from LG increased the repulsive force between modified TiO_2 nanoparticles, which simultaneously led to their better dispersion in the polymer matrix and, consequently, a smoother surface [43].

The AFM results presented in Figure 5 confirmed the presence of microphase-separated morphology on the surface of neat PU and PUCs [34,44]. It can be observed that microphase separation was more pronounced in composites with unmodified TiO_2 nanoparticles.

3.4. TEM Analysis

In order to examine the distribution of modified and unmodified TiO_2 nanoparticles within the polymer matrix, TEM analysis was carried out. Figure 6 shows TEM micrographs of the selected PUCs with 0.5 wt.% and 2 wt.% of unmodified and modified TiO_2 nanoparticles.

From the obtained TEM images, it can be noticed that the dispersion and size of the unmodified TiO_2 nanoparticles inside the PU matrix were quite different from the dispersion and size of the modified TiO_2 nanoparticles. Namely, the unmodified TiO_2 nanoparticles showed a tendency to create bigger agglomerates, the size of which increased with increasing TiO_2 nanoparticle content (between 500 and 650 nm in length). The reason for this behavior can be found in the fact that the unmodified TiO_2 nanoparticles possessed high surface free energy, high surface areas and the possibility of strong hydrogen bonding between $-\text{OH}$ groups on their surface between particles, which made it possible to group them together [9]. This agglomeration was not unexpected since other researchers also

reported similar behavior [45–47]. Contrary to this, the modified TiO₂ nanoparticles showed much better and relatively uniform dispersion inside the polymer matrix (Figure 6). Their individual sizes were much smaller than what was observed for unmodified ones (below 60 nm). This could be explained by the increased repulsive force between the modified TiO₂ particles and the improved compatibility between the TiO₂ nanoparticles and PU matrix [9,48]. The increase in the content of modified TiO₂ nanoparticles (2 wt.%) did not significantly disrupt their dispersion within the PU.

Figure 6. TEM micrographs of the selected PUCs (magnification: 60k×).

3.5. Swelling Behavior

Values of the equilibrium swelling degrees of the neat PU and prepared composites in toluene and THF, as well as the percentage of water absorption, are listed in Table 2. According to these results, values of all three parameters were lower for the neat PU than for the composites due to the decrease in the crosslinking density by the incorporation of unmodified and modified TiO₂ nanoparticles [35]. The increase of the filler content from 0.5 to 1.0 wt.% caused a further increase in the q_e values, while composites prepared with 2 wt.% of unmodified or modified TiO₂ nanoparticles showed a slight decrease in the q_e values for toluene and THF. On the other hand, the increase in filler content induced a continuous decrease in WA values. In order to explore the kinetics of the swelling of the neat PU and prepared composites in all three solvents, curve-fitting by a pseudo-second-order kinetic model was applied [34], and the obtained results are presented in Figure 7 and Table 3. High values of the correlation coefficients ($R^2 \geq 0.9974$) indicated that the applied pseudo-second-order kinetic model was a good choice. It can be observed that experimentally obtained q_e values were similar to the theoretical ones and had the same trend (Table 3). Calculated swelling rate constants showed no specific trend.

To investigate the diffusion mechanism of toluene, THF and water through the neat PU and prepared composites, the following power law expression was applied [49]:

$$\frac{w_t}{w_e} = kt^n \quad (3)$$

where k is the power law constant, n represents the exponent used to describe the diffusion mechanism and w_e and w_t are the quantities of solvent penetrating the samples at equilib-

rium and time t . Since the equation was valid only for the case when $w_t/w_e \leq 0.6$, values of the exponent n were possible to determine only for specimens swollen in water (Table 4). According to Alfrey et al., if $n < 0.5$, it can be supposed that pseudo-Fickian diffusion occurs (neat PU and PUC/Ti-0.5) [50]. In this case, it was assumed that the polymer segments had low mobility and decelerated solvent penetration, likely due to the relatively high crosslinking density. The diffusion of water through all other investigated samples could be classified as so-called non-Fickian diffusion, according to the n values.

Table 2. Values of the equilibrium swelling degree, q_e , determined in toluene and THF and the percentage of water absorption of the neat PU and its composites.

Sample	q_e Toluene	q_e THF	WA (%)
PU	0.543	1.388	4.052
PUC/Ti-0.5	0.574	1.817	9.840
PUC/Ti-1.0	0.670	1.863	5.208
PUC/Ti-2.0	0.554	1.511	3.380
PUC/LG-0.5	0.633	1.707	6.015
PUC/LG-1.0	0.716	2.033	4.856
PUC/LG-2.0	0.721	1.588	4.043

Figure 7. Swelling kinetic pseudo-second-order model for the neat PU and its composites in different solvents: (a) toluene and (b) THF.

Table 3. Values of the rate constants (k_2), theoretical equilibrium swelling degrees (q_{e2}) and correlation coefficients (R^2) of the pseudo-second-order kinetic model of the neat PU and its composites in different solvents.

Sample	Toluene			THF			Water		
	k_2 ($g\ g^{-1}\ min^{-1}$)	q_{e2}	R^2	k_2 ($g\ g^{-1}\ min^{-1}$)	q_{e2}	R^2	k_2 ($g\ g^{-1}\ min^{-1}$)	q_{e2}	R^2
PU	0.0439	0.548	0.9994	0.1233	1.389	1.0000	0.0723	0.044	0.9979
PUC/Ti-0.5	0.0350	0.583	0.9997	0.0189	1.830	0.9998	0.0418	0.105	0.9985
PUC/Ti-1.0	0.0438	0.678	0.9999	0.7696	1.864	1.0000	0.0566	0.057	0.9989
PUC/Ti-2.0	0.0783	0.557	0.9999	0.0531	1.517	1.0000	0.0316	0.042	0.9986
PUC/LG-0.5	0.0443	0.641	0.9999	0.0446	1.711	0.9999	0.0757	0.065	0.9974
PUC/LG-1.0	0.0690	0.719	0.9997	0.3727	2.034	1.0000	0.0301	0.056	0.9978
PUC/LG-2.0	0.0541	0.728	0.9999	0.0263	1.596	0.9998	0.0337	0.049	0.9983

Table 4. Values of diffusion exponent (n) in water and diffusion coefficient (D) for the neat PU and its composites in different solvents.

Sample	n	$D \times 10^8 \text{ (cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$		
		Toluene	THF	Water
PU	0.38	8.32	14.21	2.51
PUC/Ti-0.5	0.40	9.83	25.92	4.08
PUC/Ti-1.0	0.56	10.56	29.98	3.44
PUC/Ti-2.0	1.14	8.63	18.16	2.86
PUC/LG-0.5	1.00	8.22	24.01	9.58
PUC/LG-1.0	1.47	14.23	44.10	8.61
PUC/LG-2.0	1.17	15.26	20.53	5.59

The results obtained by swelling measurements were also applied to evaluate the diffusion coefficients (D) of different solvents in the prepared samples, and the calculated values are listed in Table 4 [51,52]. The increase in D values for PUCs could be attributed to the lower crosslinking density of the composites compared to that of the neat PU [35]. As expected, values of D were the highest for THF since the swelling of the prepared samples was the greatest in THF, leading to the formation of larger gaps in samples through which the solvent could be transported.

3.6. Water Contact Angle Measurements

Contact angle measurements were performed to investigate the hydrophobicity/wettability features of the prepared samples. Figure 8 presents the obtained water contact angle (WCA) values and images of the water droplets on the surface of the neat PU and its composites.

Figure 8. WCA values of the neat PU and its composites and photos of the water droplets placed on the surface of the films.

Determined WCA values were in the range of 84.4 to 97.9° for the PU/Ti samples and 86.6 to 91.1° for the PU/LG samples. It can be observed that all composite samples (except PU/Ti-2.0) had WCA values lower than those of the neat PU (96.7°). WCA was the measure of the wettability of the solids with water and depended on the chemical composition of the solid surface and surface roughness. For the chemically homogeneous hydrophobic surface, WCA increased with increasing roughness, and, contrarily, WCA decreased for rougher, chemically homogeneous hydrophilic surfaces [53–56]. According to the results shown in Figures 4 and 5 and Table 1, it can be seen that the surfaces of the tested PU and

its composites were chemically inhomogeneous and had very different roughness and, therefore, the obtained WCA values varied.

4. Conclusions

The structure, morphology and hydrophobicity of the prepared PU network and its composites, based on unmodified and surface-modified TiO₂ nanoparticles (0.5, 1 and 2 wt.%), were investigated in this study. The conducted analyses showed that the added TiO₂ nanoparticles affected the cross-sectional and surface morphology, swelling behavior, and hydrophobicity of the prepared PU. The cross-sectional morphology of the PUCs prepared using lower contents of unmodified or modified TiO₂ nanoparticles was less irregular and smoother, while, in PUCs with a higher content of TiO₂ nanoparticles, certain microstructures (clusters or agglomerates) of various sizes were created. AFM analysis confirmed the existence of a two-phase morphology. TEM analysis showed that the surface modification of the TiO₂ nanoparticles with LG gave a much better, uniform and homogeneous dispersion of TiO₂ nanoparticles inside the PU in comparison to the unmodified ones. According to the results obtained by the swelling measurements, the incorporation of unmodified and modified TiO₂ nanoparticles led to a decrease in the crosslinking density of the PU network. Also, the obtained results showed that the kinetics of the swelling of the neat PU and prepared composites in THF, toluene and water could be described by a pseudo-second-order kinetic model. Based on the presented results, prepared PUCs may be considered to have potential usage as protective coatings.

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